

Split Point

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1 PROGRAM NOTES

Split Point is a quiet ambient work which explores inclusion and constraint [5] and the redistribution of musical processes in contemporary piano music. In a collaboration between inclusive music collective The Wired Ensemble and experimental pianist Alex Lucas, the piano is played collectively, over a network, through the use of reductionist [2], accessible interfaces. In this configuration, the piano is considered a hyper-instrument [1] with parameters such as pitch, rhythm and timbre, split and redistributed amongst the group. We invite the audience to consider if it is musically interesting to split the piano in such a way and if an individual can communicate independent creative expression when using binary on-off controllers; a common goal in inclusive music [4].

2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The Wired Ensemble is a Belfast-based collective of disabled musicians and composers supported by the Drake Music Project Northern Ireland. Initially founded in 1999 by Professor Frank Lyons, the group has enjoyed various successes, including multiple performances at the Sonorities contemporary music festival and collaborations with acclaimed artists such as violinist Darragh Morgan [3]. Music technology is pivotal in providing ensemble members with access to musicking, with the group utilising both commercially available devices and bespoke technologies developed in collaboration with academic institutions such as Queen's University Belfast.

Before returning to academia to pursue research into accessible music technology, non-disabled pianist Alex Lucas collaborated with sound artist and composer Olan Mill on a handful of modern classical albums, resulting in performances in Spain and across the UK. Together, The Wired Ensemble and Alex are keen to promote inclusion in music. Rather than working in isolation, disabled and non-musicians musicians each benefit from working with one another.

3 PERFORMANCE NOTES

The individual members of Wired Ensemble utilise standard text-entry computer keyboards as accessible music

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Fig. 1. Image Credit: Marcus Gjenaar - <https://unsplash.com/photos/v318kTbPhzA>

controllers. Binary signals from these keyboards are transmitted via the internet to a central computer, and are then used to control custom music and visualisation software.

4 MEDIA LINKS

- Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Oe0uaQCItg>
- Audio: <https://hawkmoonrecords.bandcamp.com/album/tramuntana>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The performers would like to thank the Drake Music Project Northern Ireland for their continued support and the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) for funding this collaboration.

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